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MOTIVATIONS AND CHALLENGES IN READING LITERATURE AMONG GEN Z COLLEGE STUDENTS- A QUANTITATIVE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the motivations and challenges in reading literature among Generation Z college students at Abuyog Community College. Using a quantitative descriptive-comparative design, a total enumeration of 54 third year BSED English majors participated through a validated online survey. Results showed that personal growth (WM=3.14) and academic requirements (WM=3.09) were the strongest motivators, while social influence (WM=2.99) and personal enjoyment (WM=3.02) also played significant roles. Conversely, the main challenges identified were time constraints (WM=2.91) and digital distractions (WM=2.88), followed by language and comprehension difficulties (WM=2.84). The relatability of themes posed a lesser challenge (WM=2.58). ANOVA results indicated no significant differences in motivations and challenges based on age and gender ($p>0.05$). These findings suggest that interventions to improve literature engagement should focus on integrating relatable texts, leveraging technology, and providing structured opportunities for reading that align with modern learners' interests. This study highlights the need to balance traditional literary education with digital-age innovations to foster sustained reading habits among Generation Z students.

Keywords: generation z, reading motivation, reading challenges, literature engagement, digital natives, reading habits

Introduction

Reading habits have significantly changed across generations with technology having the most impact on generation Z - people born in between mid-1990s to early 2000s (Pramerta, 2024). Digital Natives also known as "digital natives" (Yoesoef, 2020) generations who is exposed to digital technologies since childhood which are shaping their preferences and behaviour including interaction with literature.

The presence of electronic devices and digital environments have exchanged the way in which reading was traditionally proposed. Booknovels, online novels are easy to get into with just a few clicks. An increasing number of Gen Z readers are choosing digital content, as shown in the 2024 Wattpad Poll when more than 83% indicated a preference to online staying sources. And more than 80% are actively looking for stories that focus on inclusivity and representation.

As access to literature increases, however, obstacles continue to frustrate Gen Z's participation in it. There is a heavy reliance on digital media that leads to shorter attention spans and thus less depth of engagement with complex readings (Twenge, 2017). Also, the rise of fast-reading platforms like TikTok, Facebook and YouTube favors short entertaining content over intellectually stimulating reading. This trend is a threat to higher level skills, such as analysis and synthesis. As such, the

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researchers prompted to determine and quantify the motivations that encourage Gen Z to read literature and the challenges that prevent them from deeper engagement. Insights from this research may guide educators, publishers, and policymakers in developing strategies to foster meaningful literary engagement among digital-native students.

Statement of the Problem

This study addressed the following research questions:

1. What are the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a) Age
 - b) Gender
2. Identify the motivations of Generation Z college students in reading literature in terms of:
 - a) Personal enjoyment
 - b) Academic requirements
 - c) Social influence
 - d) Personal growth or self-improvement
3. Determine the challenges faced by Generation Z students in reading literature regarding:
 - a) Language and comprehension difficulty
 - b) Time constraints
 - c) Digital or multimedia distractions
 - d) Relevance or relatability of themes
4. Assess whether there are significant differences in motivations and challenges based on demographic factors in terms of age and gender.
5. Propose potential interventions to address reading challenges among Generation Z college students.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative descriptive-comparative research design which examined the motivations and challenges in reading literature among Generation Z college students. This design allowed measuring the motivation levels, challenges, and relationships, enabling comparisons across demographic groups and proposing targeted interventions based on measurable trends.

Research Respondents

The study involved 54 third-year Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English students at Abuyog Community College. Total enumeration sampling was used due to the small, accessible population. The third-year level was chosen because these students take multiple literature subjects, making them highly engaged and relevant for the study's objectives.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at Abuyog Community College in Abuyog, Leyte. The school was selected for its accessibility and diverse student population across academic programs. The school provided a relevant context for exploring how Generation Z students engage with literature in a provincial college environment.

Research Instruments

The researchers utilized a survey questionnaire designed by the researchers. The questionnaire consisted of three sections. The first part aimed to gather the respondents' demographic profiles in terms of their age and gender. The second part will have two sections: Section A assessed the students' motivations in reading literature; and Section B determined their challenges in reading literature. Each section used a 4-point Likert scale, answerable by Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree. The last part asked the respondents about various reading solutions and interventions. The questionnaire was administered online through Google Forms to ensure accessibility and convenience for all respondents.

Data Gathering Procedure

Prior to collecting the necessary data from the respondents, the researchers sought permission from the college president to conduct a survey. Once approval was granted, the researchers prepared the survey questionnaire validated by an expert to ensure its clarity, relevance, and content validity.

After validation, the survey was conducted using Google Forms. The researchers asked assistance from the respondents' course instructor in disseminating the survey link to their class group chat. The purpose of the study and confidentiality of the responses were thoroughly explained to the respondents, with the respondents' consent being obtained before proceeding with the questionnaire. The survey link remained open for responses for three days, with follow-up reminders sent to ensure maximum participation. After the given period, the researchers organized the responses by downloading them into a spreadsheet format for statistical analysis.

Ethical Consideration

Prior to participation, all respondents were provided with a clear explanation of the study's objectives, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. All data collected were handled in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173) and institutional policies. All data were collected anonymously to safeguard respondents' privacy, with their responses kept confidential and solely used for academic purposes.

Method of Scoring and Interpretation

1. Respondents' Demographic Profile Variables

Sex	Code
Male	1
Female	2

2. Likert Scale

- 4 – Strongly Agree
- 3 – Agree
- 2 – Disagree
- 1 – Strongly Disagree

3. Mean Scores Interpretation

Weighted Mean Range	Verbal Interpretation
3.26 – 4.00	Strongly Agree
2.51 – 3.25	Agree
1.76 – 2.50	Disagree
1.00 – 1.75	Strongly Disagree

Data Analysis

The researchers used SPSS to analyze the collected data. Descriptive Statistics, including frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation was used to determine the demographic profiles of the respondents in terms of age and gender. On the other hand, the researchers tallied the responses and computed the weighted mean to determine the levels of motivation and challenges of the respondents in reading literature. ANOVA was used in finding out if there is a significant difference in the respondents' motivation and challenges based on their demographic profiles e.g., age and gender.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Demographic Profile

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Age		
16 – 19	5	9.3%
20 – 22	40	74.1%
23 – 25	3	5.6%
26 – 28	6	11.1%
Total	54	100%
Gender		
Male	9	16.7%
Female	45	83.3%
Total	54	100%

Table 1 indicates that 74.1% of the respondents were between 20-22 years old and generally female (83.3%). This shows that the sample mainly consists of young adult females belonging to Generation Z. Previous research supports this finding, as women have been shown to engage more frequently in leisure reading compared to men (Clark & Piction, 2020).

Weighted Mean on the Motivations in Reading Literature

Table 2.1. Personal Enjoyment

A. Personal Enjoyment	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
M1. I read literature because I enjoy exploring different stories and worlds.	3.04	Agree
M2. Reading literature helps me relax and relieve stress.	2.93	Agree
M3. I feel emotionally connected to the characters and events in the stories I read.	3.19	Agree
M4. I read literature to escape from daily stress or problems.	2.91	Agree

M5. I look forward to reading literature even without it being required.	3.04	Agree
AVERAGE	3.02	Agree

As presented in Table 2.1, the highest-rated item was M3 (WM=3.19), indicating that students form emotional bonds with the literature they consume. The lowest-rated statement was M4 (WM=2.91). With an overall average of 3.02, the results show that students generally agree that reading literature gives them personal enjoyment, aligning the Self-Determination Theory of Ryan and Deci (2020), suggesting that intrinsic motivation plays a vital role in sustained engagement with reading.

Table 2.2. Academic Requirements

B. Academic Requirements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
M6. I read literary texts mainly to fulfill school requirements.	2.89	Agree
M7. My grades and academic performance motivate me to read.	3.11	Agree
M8. Teachers or instructors encourage me to read literature.	3.26	Strongly Agree
M9. I read to prepare for class recitations and discussions.	3.13	Agree
M10. I read literature to perform better in exams and assignments.	3.06	Agree
AVERAGE	3.09	Agree

Table 2.2 reveals that M8 obtained the highest weighted mean at 3.26, showing that teacher influence strongly motivates students. On the other hand, M6 rated low at 2.89. The overall average of 3.09 poses that academic-related motivations strongly shape students' reading behavior, supporting Guthrie and Wigfield's (2000) findings that extrinsic motivators significantly influence the students' willingness to read.

Table 2.3. Social Influence

C. Social Influence	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
M11. My friends or classmates influence my reading choices.	2.63	Agree
M12. Social media platforms (e.g., TikTok, Wattpad) inspire me to read literature.	2.98	Agree
M13. I like joining discussions about books with peers or online groups.	2.87	Agree
M14. Reading literature makes me feel connected to a community.	3.04	Agree
M15. Influencers and bloggers motivate me to read certain titles.	3.44	Strongly Agree
AVERAGE	2.99	Agree

Table 2.3 shows that M15 rated highest (WM=3.44) and M11 rated lowest (WM=2.63), indicating that influence from digital personalities and online platforms help in shaping reading preferences. With an overall average of 2.99, the results indicate that social influence is fair and largely originating from

online communities instead of face-to-face interactions, highlighting the role of social media platforms as key shapers of Gen Z's reading habits (Twenge, 2017; Pramerta, 2024).

Table 2.4 Personal Growth or Self Improvement

D. Personal Growth or Self Improvement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
M16. Reading literature helps me develop critical thinking skills.	3.13	Agree
M17. Reading improves my vocabulary and language skills.	3.19	Agree
M18. Literature broadens my perspective on culture and society	3.20	Agree
M19. I use literature to grow intellectually and emotionally.	3.07	Agree
M20. Reading helps me develop lifelong learning habits.	3.15	Agree
AVERAGE	3.14	Agree

As shown in Table 2.4, M18 received highest ratings (WM=3.20). Contrary to M19 (WM=3.07), revealing that students view literature as a tool for cultural and intellectual development. Based on the average of 3.14, this shows that students generally agree that literature fosters both cognitive growth and empathy, contributing to holistic personal development (Rosenblatt, 1995).

Weighted Mean on the Challenges in Reading Literature

Table 3.1. Language and Comprehension Difficulty

A. Language and Comprehension Difficulty	Mean	Verbal interpretation
C1. The language used in literary works is difficult to understand.	2.67	Agree
C2. I struggle with unfamiliar words and phrases in texts.	3.00	Agree
C3. I have difficulty understanding figurative language or symbolism.	2.70	Agree
C4. Some texts are written in outdated language, which confuses me.	2.96	Agree
C5. I need external help (summaries, guides) to understand the text.	2.89	Agree
AVERAGE	2.84	Agree

Table 3.1 shows that C2 is the main challenge in reading literature (WM=3.00), while C1 as the least (WM=2.67). The overall average of 2.84 proves suggests that while students moderately have trouble with comprehension, most struggle with limited vocabulary and figurative language, echoing Snow's (2010) findings that highlighted the importance of language scaffolding in improving literary comprehension.

Table 3.2. Time Constraints

B. Time Constraints	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
C6. I lack time to read because of academic workload.	2.94	Agree
C7. Household responsibilities prevent me from reading regularly.	2.96	Agree
C8. Reading long texts consumes too much of my time.	2.80	Agree
C9. I struggle to maintain a reading schedule.	2.98	Agree
C10. I prioritize other subjects over reading literature.	2.87	Agree
AVERAGE	2.91	Agree

Table 3.2 reveals that C9 had the highest mean (WM=2.98), while C8 scored lowest (WM=2.80). The results show that at 2.91, lack of time appears to be a major barrier to reading. This reflects Gen Z's busy academic schedules and competing responsibilities, leaving literature at the back of their priorities (Schunk et.al., 2014), suggesting a need for structured programs that integrate reading into feasible routines.

Table 3.3. Digital and Multimedia Distractions

C. Digital and Multimedia Distractions	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
C11. I often get distracted by social media while reading.	3.00	Agree
C12. I prefer watching videos over reading books.	2.93	Agree
C13. I feel tempted to multitask online while reading.	2.87	Agree
C14. Streaming services are more appealing to me than reading.	2.67	Agree
C15. Digital distractions decrease my motivation to read literature.	2.94	Agree
AVERAGE	2.88	Agree

As seen in Table 3.3, C11 was the most agreed-upon statement (WM=3.00). The lowest rated was C14 (WM=2.67). The overall average of 2.88 indicates that digital distractions pose a significant impact on students' reading focus, supporting Twenge's (2017) claim that the availability of fast-paced content leads to short attention spans and lesser interaction with texts.

Table 3.4. Relevance or Relatability of Themes

D. Relevance or Relatability of Themes	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
C16. I find it hard to relate to the themes of assigned texts.	2.52	Agree
C17. Most literary works do not reflect modern issues or trends.	2.46	Disagree
C18. The stories I read feel distant from my personal experiences.	2.57	Agree
C19. Literature classes focus on old works I cannot connect with.	2.50	Disagree
C20. I would read more if themes were more relatable to my generation.	2.85	Agree
AVERAGE	2.58	Agree

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Table 3.4 shows that C20 received the highest mean ($WM=2.85$), while C17 had the lowest ($WM=2.46$). Based on the average of 2.58, the results show that students moderately agree that lack of relatability can hinder reading motivation. While being the least-rated challenge, it still highlights the need to integrate contemporary texts that resonate with the students' personal experiences and current societal issues (Appleman, 2015).

Significant Difference in Motivation and Challenges Based on Demographic Profiles

Table 4.1. Significant Difference in Motivation

Demographic Factor	F-value	p-value (Sig.)	Interpretation
Age	0.783	0.605	Not Significant
Gender	0.192	0.663	Not Significant

Table 4.2. Significant Difference in Challenges

Demographic Factor	F-value	p-value (Sig.)	Interpretation
Age	1.889	0.093	Not Significant
Gender	0.284	0.596	Not Significant

Table 4.1 and 4.2 present the ANOVA results between the motivations and challenges based on the demographic profiles of the respondent, which indicate no significant differences in motivation and challenges based on age and gender ($p>0.05$). This implies that both male and female students, regardless of age, share similar experiences when it comes to reading literature. These results suggest that interventions to improve reading engagement can be implemented broadly without the need for demographic-specific strategies (Cresswell & Cresswell, 2018).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study found that Generation Z college students are motivated to read literature for personal growth and academic reasons but face challenges like time constraints and digital distractions. Age and gender do not significantly affect their reading motivations or challenges. To support their reading habits, educators should integrate relatable contemporary texts, use technology, and create interactive, student-centered literature programs that connect with students' experiences and digital preferences, promoting both intellectual growth and a lifelong love of reading.

In line with the conclusions the researchers propose a "Relatable and Interactive Literature Engagement Program" for Generation Z that offers reading materials reflecting their life experiences and cultural backgrounds. The program uses technology like e-books and online platforms, allowing students to choose texts such as graphic novels and fan fiction. Teachers facilitate interactive discussions connecting literature to current social themes in a safe, inclusive environment. This approach aims to create dynamic, student-centered literature classes that enhance comprehension, enjoyment, cognitive growth, emotional engagement, and lifelong reading habits.

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